

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN THE REPATRIATION SERVICE OF DISPLACED PERSONS BY THE SOCIAL SERVICE OF WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT AND CHILD PROTECTION OF BALI PROVINCE

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Abstract

The government has the main responsibility to ensure social welfare, including abandoned services. As a migration location, Bali Province faces social problems because many displaced people need to be repatriated to their place of origin. The purpose of this study is to study the role of government cooperation in providing services for the repatriation of displaced persons by the Social Service for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province. This study uses a descriptive qualitative method and collects data through field observations, interviews, and documentation with important informants, including relevant agency officials and community members. Preliminary results show that the collaborative governance model involves cooperation between government agencies, NGOs, communities, and other non-governmental actors in formulating plans and implementing repatriation services. Building trust and accountability between parties and overcoming resource limitations requires effective cooperation. The study found that government cooperation is an effective method to improve the efficiency and quality of social services, especially for vulnerable groups such as displaced people. It is hoped that this research will contribute to the development of inclusive and sustainable social service policies in the future.

Keywords: *Collaborative Governance, Public Service, Displaced People, Social Service, Bali.*

INTRODUCTION

The Government of the Republic of Indonesia as stated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia is a democratic, decentralized government, free from Collusion, Corruption, and Nepotism (KKN), and can carry out public services in a fair manner. The government's duty is to serve the community by providing these services (Syamsuadi & Abdurrab, 2017). To regulate this, the government made Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services. This law states that the state is obliged to serve every citizen with public services, as mandated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Public service is defined as any activity or series of activities that meet the service needs of each citizen and resident, according to laws and regulations. This includes goods, services, and/or administrative services provided by public service providers. Law Number 25 of 2009, article 4 states the following principles of public service implementation: public interest, legal certainty, equality of rights, balance of rights and obligations, professionalism, participation, equal treatment, openness, accountability, facilities and special treatment for vulnerable groups, timeliness, and speed, convenience, and affordability.

According to the journal (Warsono et al., 2023) Collaborative Governance is seen as an alternative that can help accelerate and implement Government programs, Collaborative Governance is a process in which various stakeholders work together. This collaboration involves sharing visions, goals, strategies, and activities. Each party has the power to make its own decisions and manage its organization, but everything is subject to mutual agreement. Collaborative Governance mainly tries to solve a specific problem or issue for the parties involved. These parties include government and non-governmental groups. The principles of good governance also involve stakeholders and civil society in creating and deciding on solutions. Cooperation begins because each party has limited capacity, resources, or networks. By working together, they can combine different parts to help achieve a common goal. When it comes to creating common goals, visions, missions, norms, and values, each party has an equal position. They can make their own decisions but must follow a mutual agreement. So, Collaborative Governance is when stakeholders work together based on shared principles to achieve specific goals, such as developing the tourism sector, which is also the task of the government.

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Indonesia is one of the developing countries. It is only natural that people in a country want to have a good life. Society, especially humans, want to live a prosperous life. This is because well-being is one of the keys to happiness. People want to move to higher income areas because they have many needs and desires. The economy is one of the factors that make people move to seek a better life, leaving their hometowns because they believe that life elsewhere can be better. This state of mind creates an interesting mindset for many people. This gives rise to a belief, especially in rural areas, that "To be successful, you have to leave your hometown." Some migrants do succeed elsewhere, which encourages others to migrate with them. However, many also fail, causing problems for themselves and others. Bali Province is a popular destination for migrants looking for work. Denpasar is also a promising place for migrants because it is the capital of Bali Province and has many jobs, so there is a movement from one area to another. This displacement poses problems for migrants, communities, and governments. These problems arise because they are unable to adjust to a new life in a new place for a variety of reasons, such as not having a permanent job, a family in the area, or enough money to live. Another consequence is that they often want to return home but have no money, and they have nowhere to live or work, so they are abandoned. The government is responsible for helping these displaced people. The Bali Provincial Social Service in the Social Rehabilitation Sector is the government agency responsible for this. Displaced people are individuals, families, or groups who are abandoned, both in Indonesia and abroad, for ideological, political, economic, or socio-cultural reasons. They want to return home but don't have the resources to do so. Displaced people are considered a type of social disaster because their situation is unpredictable, sudden, unplanned, and impossible to predict. (Tegal *et al.*, 2020) in their research explained that in repatriating displaced residents, there are several rules that apply. The repatriation of displaced people can be done by repatriating them directly to their place of origin in the same province or to another province. The Bali Provincial Social Service helps displaced residents to return outside Bali. The following are the rules for the repatriation of displaced people set by the Bali Provincial Social Service:

1. Displaced residents must have the status of Indonesian citizens and will leave for the province nearby, such as East Java or West Nusa Tenggara.
2. Indonesian citizens who are displaced must be physically and spiritually healthy.
3. Displaced Indonesian citizens who are physically and spiritually unwell must be accompanied by family or other people.

If this rule is followed, there are several things that need to be done to help the repatriation of displaced people. This is done to prove that they really want to return to their hometown and meet the requirements to be repatriated. The following are the requirements set:

1. Letter of reference from the Regency or City Social Service in Bali Province.
2. A letter of reference from the Social Service of other districts, cities, or provinces.
3. Referral letter from relevant agencies, such as the police, hospital, or institution correctional facilities, both in Bali and those not.

Based on the above problems, the author wants to examine how the Government and various parties work together to assist the Bali Provincial Social Service in repatriating refugees.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used is comprehensive and structured. The discussion included the location of the research, research design, types and sources of data, data collection techniques, research informants, data validity examination techniques, and data analysis techniques. This description aims to provide a clear understanding of the research process carried out, so that the research results can be scientifically accounted for. This research was carried out at the Office of Social Service, Women's Empowerment, and Child Protection of Bali Province. The selection of the research location is based on the consideration that the agency is an official government institution that has the authority to implement Social Rehabilitation, especially in handling and repatriating displaced people. Through the Social Rehabilitation Sector, this agency plays a direct role in the implementation of the repatriation program for displaced people, so that the research location is considered relevant to the focus of the study being conducted. The research design used in this study is qualitative research with a descriptive approach. The qualitative approach was chosen because this research aims to understand and describe in depth the social phenomena that occur in the field. According to Creswell (2013), qualitative research is a process to explore and understand the meaning derived from social problems. The descriptive approach is used to systematically describe how the application of collaborative governance in assisting the Bali Provincial Social Service in repatriating displaced residents. The data obtained is presented in the form of a narrative description using words, as stated by Moleong (2013) that qualitative research produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from the subjects studied. In this context, in-depth interviews are the main technique so that the selection of the right informants greatly determines the quality of the

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research data. The type of data used in this study consists of primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained directly from the main sources in the field through interviews with parties who knew and were directly involved in the implementation of the repatriation program, as well as through direct observation of social rehabilitation activities and processes. Meanwhile, secondary data is obtained through literature studies by examining and analyzing various written sources, such as books, scientific journals, laws and regulations, official documents, and other scientific works relevant to the research topic. Data collection in this study was carried out through several techniques, namely interviews, observations, and documentation. Interviews were conducted in depth by asking oral questions to informants to obtain information about their views, experiences, and roles in implementing collaborative governance in the process of repatriating displaced persons. Observations were carried out by directly observing service activities and coordination between parties in handling displaced people, so that researchers obtained a clear picture of the conditions and processes that occurred in the field. Documentation is done by collecting and studying relevant documents, such as regulations, activity reports, and official archives that support research data.

Research informants are selected purposively, namely based on the consideration that the informant has knowledge, experience, and direct involvement with the research focus. The informants in this study include the Head of the Bali Provincial Social Service, Women's Empowerment, and Child Protection as the Head of the Regional Apparatus Organization, the Secretary of the Social Service, the Head of the Social Rehabilitation Division, and the surrounding community who have encountered or interacted with displaced residents. To ensure the validity of the data, this study uses data validity criteria according to Moleong, namely credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. The credibility of the data is maintained through the extension of observations, increasing diligence, triangulation of sources, techniques and time, analysis of negative cases, the use of reference materials, and member checks to informants. Transferability is carried out by presenting a detailed and clear description of the research so that the research results can be understood and applied to other similar contexts. Dependability is carried out by systematically reviewing the entire research process so that the research can be replicated with the same procedure. Confirmability is done to ensure that the research results really come from the research data and process, not from the subjectivity of the researcher. The data analysis technique in this study is carried out qualitatively with the stages of data reduction, data presentation, as well as drawing conclusions and verification. Data reduction is carried out by selecting and focusing data that is relevant to the research objectives so that the data becomes more organized and easy to analyze. The data that has been reduced is then presented in the form of a systematic narrative description so that it makes it easier to understand and draw conclusions. The final stage of data analysis is conclusion drawing and verification, which is carried out by comparing research findings with relevant concepts and theories, as well as re-examining the data continuously until valid and scientifically accountable conclusions are obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Informants

The characteristics of the informants of this study reflect the diversity of essential roles and responsibilities in supporting the implementation of the Repatriation of Displaced Persons. The informants consisting of four individuals have different but complementary strategic positions. The Head of the Bali Provincial Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Social Service has a major role in supervising and coordinating the overall policies and programs for the repatriation of displaced persons assisted by the Secretary of the Service who ensures the smooth running of the agency's internal operations. The Head of Social Rehabilitation is responsible for the management and supervision of the social rehabilitation process, which includes the Repatriation of Displaced Persons program. The process of repatriating displaced persons starting from complaints/reports, finding of displaced persons, repatriation to the area of origin and supervision of displaced persons arriving in the area of origin is the responsibility of the Head of Social Rehabilitation. The community/NGOs also play a very important role in the process of environmental monitoring whether indications of displaced people are found who can then report or escort the displaced person to the Social Service for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province for further repatriation process by the Social Service for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province. Displaced people who will be returned to their home areas by the Social Service for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province are used as informants in the Displaced Persons Repatriation program as a continuation of the implementation of the program. Starting from data collection to finally the process of repatriation to the area of origin, the author hopes to get criticism and suggestions for this program for the repatriation of displaced people.

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Informants

Yes	Initials	Gender	Age	Informant Code
1	AASMD	Women	53	I1
2	NPYC	Women	40	I2
3	IKS	Women	43	I3
4	Stuttgart	Male	37	I4

Overview of the Repatriation Services of the Displaced Persons by the Social Service, Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province

The handling of the repatriation service of displaced persons by the Bali Provincial Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Social Service is carried out through a series of structured stages, ranging from initial outreach, data collection, temporary handling, to facilitation of repatriation to the area of origin. The results of the study show that the service plays the role of the main actor who coordinates the entire service process by involving various related parties according to the needs of the cases handled. In the early stages, the Social Service conducted outreach and data collection on displaced people found in the Bali Province area. Data collection includes the identity, social conditions, and regional origin of displaced people. However, in practice, data limitations are often found, so the agency must carry out further coordination with other agencies to complete the information. An informant said:

"Our first step is usually data collection first. But often the data is incomplete, so we have to investigate again with other parties." – I3

After the data collection process, the Social Service provides temporary treatment to displaced people according to the conditions faced. This treatment can be in the form of temporary placement in a halfway house, provision of basic needs, and social assistance before repatriation. In this stage, the agency also considers the humanitarian and security aspects of displaced people, especially for vulnerable groups. This is as expressed by the following informants:

"We did not immediately repatriate, but first looked at the condition. If you need to be safe, you need to be safe." – I2

The next stage is coordination with the local government of the displaced person's origin to ensure the readiness of the reception and the smooth repatriation process. The Bali Provincial Social Service plays a role in facilitating cross-regional communication and ensuring that repatriation is carried out in accordance with applicable procedures. The head of the field in charge of social services said that this coordination is an important part of the duties of the service:

"We coordinate with the area of origin to ensure displaced people are truly accepted and treated after they are repatriated." – I2

Overall, the results of the study show that the handling of the repatriation service of displaced persons by the Bali Provincial Social Service is carried out in stages and coordinated, by adjusting service procedures to real conditions in the field. The role of the service as the main coordinator is key in ensuring that repatriation services are not only carried out administratively, but also pay attention to aspects of social protection and the sustainability of the handling of displaced people after returning to their areas of origin.

Analysis of Collaborative Governance in the Repatriation Service of Displaced Persons by the Social Service of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province

To understand the Collaborative Governance implemented through the Repatriation of Displaced People program by the Bali Provincial Social Service, this study conducted a focus analysis on the Collaborative Governance model. Ansell & Gash explains that Collaborative Governance is a collective decision-making process that involves governments and non-government actors directly in formal forums to reach consensus and implement common public policies. The model consists of four main components (or process stages) that are interconnected and form a collaborative cycle:

1. Starting Conditions

The initial conditions describe the situation that existed before the collaboration began, including the level of balance of power and resources, the incentives to participate, and the history of relationships between actors. If the initial relationship is colored by trust, a balance of power, and clear incentives, then the collaboration will run more smoothly. Conversely, if there is a power imbalance or a history of conflict, the collaborative process takes longer to build trust and commitment. In the context of the Bali Provincial PPPA

Social Service, this initial condition can be seen from the extent to which actors such as social institutions, the police, and local governments have the same balance of roles and motivations in handling the repatriation of displaced people.

2. Institutional Design

Institutional design refers to the formal structures, rules, and mechanisms that frame the collaborative process. Ansell and Gash emphasized the importance of forums that are inclusive, transparent, and have mutually agreed upon basic rules, such as role-sharing, communication procedures, and decision-making mechanisms. Good institutional design creates a sense of fairness and guarantees all parties have a voice in the process. In the context of the Social Service, this design can be in the form of the formation of a cross-agency coordination team or the preparation of SOPs for handling displaced persons that are clear and agreed upon by all parties.

3. Collaborative Process

The collaborative process is at the heart of the model because this is where real interaction between actors takes place. This process includes *face-to-face dialogue*, *trust building*, commitment to the process, the formation of *shared understanding*, and the achievement of *intermediate outcomes*. Through open communication and growing trust, actors can unite goals and solve problems collectively. In the program for the repatriation of displaced persons, this can be seen through routine coordination between agencies and direct cooperation in the field during the repatriation process.

4. Outcomes

This stage reflects the tangible results of the collaborative process, both in the form of policy outputs, increased program effectiveness, and long-term trust building. The results achieved are not only measured by the success of the program, but also by strengthening inter-stakeholder relationships, building institutional capacity, and institutional *learning*. In the context of Bali, the final results of the collaboration can be seen from the increasing effectiveness of the repatriation of displaced persons, increased coordination between agencies, and the formation of strong social networks for the handling of similar cases in the future.

Thus, the *Collaborative Governance* model put forward by Ansell and Gash (2008) provides a comprehensive conceptual framework to understand how collaboration between public actors can be formed and run effectively. The four main components, namely *starting conditions*, *institutional design*, *collaborative process*, and *outcomes*, form a unified process that influences each other in creating sustainable collaborative governance. In the next section, each of these components will be discussed in more depth to explore how this model is applied in the context of the Repatriation of Displaced Persons program by the Bali Provincial PPPA Social Service.

Starting Conditions (Kondisi Awal)

The initial condition of collaboration in the service of repatriating displaced persons was marked by the limited capacity of one agency to handle problems independently. Displaced people generally face complex problems, such as not having an identity, coming from outside the region, and needing cross-sector handling. This condition encourages the need for cooperation between institutions from the beginning of the service process. This is as expressed by the following informant:

"The cases of displaced people are diverse, some do not have identities, some are from outside Bali. If it is handled alone, it is clearly not possible, so from the beginning it must involve many parties." - II

In addition to the complexity of the problems faced by displaced people, the initial conditions of collaboration are also influenced by the limited resources owned by each agency. These limitations include human resources, budgets, and service support facilities. In certain situations, this limitation causes agencies to be unable to carry out all stages of repatriation services optimally without support from other parties. This encourages the formation of inter-institutional dependency from the early stages of handling displaced people. An informant revealed:

"If you only rely on one agency, it will definitely not be enough, both in terms of officers and budget. That's why from the beginning we have to support each other."

The initial condition of collaboration is also marked by the need for accurate and fast information related to the identity and origin of displaced people's regions. Incomplete data is often the main obstacle in determining repatriation steps, requiring the involvement of other actors such as the local government of origin and police officers. In this context, collaboration is a means to complement each other with information and speed up the decision-making process. As stated by the informant:

"Many people are displaced whose data is unclear, so we have to coordinate with other regions or the police to ascertain their origin before they are sent home."

Thus, the initial conditions of collaboration in the repatriation service of displaced persons were not only influenced by the complexity of the cases handled, but also by the limited resources and the need for cross-sectoral information support. This condition strengthens the urgency of implementing collaborative governance as an approach that allows the involvement of various actors from the early stages of service.

Institutional Design in Handling Repatriation Services for Displaced Persons

In the framework of *collaborative governance*, *institutional design* refers to institutional arrangements that include the division of roles, ground rules, coordination mechanisms, and the level of inclusivity of the actors involved in the collaboration. According to Chris Ansell and Alison Gash, good institutional design should be able to create clarity of roles and encourage equal participation of actors to support the effectiveness of collaboration. In the context of this study, institutional design is an important element to understand how the Bali Provincial Social Service handles the repatriation services of displaced persons. The results of the study show that the handling of repatriation services for displaced persons by the Bali Provincial Social Service for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection is carried out through cross-agency role sharing that is functional and adaptive. The Bali Provincial Social Service plays the role of the main coordinator, while the district/city government, police officers, and social institutions carry out their functions according to their respective authorities. This pattern is in line with the findings of Feblianto *et al.* (2024) who stated that *collaborative governance* in public services in Indonesia generally develops through the division of practical roles between actors, although it is not always supported by specific technical regulations.

However, institutional design in this collaboration tends to rely more on informal mechanisms than formal arrangements. Cooperation between actors is mostly based on general regulations of social services, previous cooperation experience, and situational cross-agency communication. This condition is in line with the findings of Maharudin (2022) who show that the institutional design of *collaborative governance* in the public service sector is often flexible, but has weaknesses in terms of consistency and procedural certainty. From the perspective of the second research objective, this condition shows that the Bali Provincial PPPA Social Service handles the repatriation service of displaced persons through an institutional approach that is adaptive to field dynamics. The flexibility of institutional design allows the agency to respond to cases quickly and contextually. However, on the other hand, the limitations of formal arrangements have the potential to create a dependence on individual initiative and personal relationships between actors, so that collaboration has not been fully institutionalized strongly. These findings are in line with the results of research by Pratama and Nugroho (2021) which states that *institutional design* that is not yet established in cross-sector collaboration can hinder the sustainability of cooperation, especially when there is a change of actors or changes in organizational structure. Thus, although the institutional design implemented by the Bali Provincial PPPA Social Service has supported the implementation of repatriation services for displaced persons, strengthening formal institutional aspects is still needed so that collaboration can run more stable and sustainable.

Collaborative Process in the Implementation of Repatriation of Displaced Persons

Based on the results of the study, the collaborative process in the repatriation service of displaced persons coordinated by the Social Service for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of Bali Province showed a dynamic and contextual pattern of interaction. Collaboration does not take place in a linear manner, but develops through repeated communication between actors from the outreach stage to the repatriation to the area of origin. This pattern is in line with the view of Ansell and Gash who emphasize that the collaborative process is a continuous cycle of interaction influenced by the conditions of the case and the actors' responses. The results of the study show that face-to-face dialogue and communication between agencies are the initial mechanism in the collaboration process. Dialogue is carried out both through formal forums and informal communication to equalize understanding regarding the condition of displaced people and the handling steps to be taken. In the context of the repatriation of displaced persons, this flexibility of communication is important because the characteristics of cases are often urgent and require quick decisions. This shows that dialogue in *collaborative processes* does not always manifest itself in the form of formal deliberations, but also through practical interactions oriented towards problem solving. In the framework of *collaborative governance*, this kind of dialogue serves as a starting space for the formation of understanding and coordination of actions. Emerson and Nabatchi (2021) affirm that the effectiveness of collaborative dialogue lies in its ability to adapt to the complexity of public issues. Thus, the formal and informal communication practices found in this study can be understood as the adaptation of actors to the demands of the repatriation service of displaced persons.

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In addition to dialogue, the collaborative process is also supported by trust between actors formed from previous cooperation experiences. This trust allows the division of tasks and decision-making to be done more quickly without having to wait for formal instructions. In the context of the Bali Provincial PPPA Social Service, interagency trust plays a role as social capital that facilitates coordination, especially in field situations that require immediate response. These findings are in line with the view of Sørensen and Torfing (2022) who stated that trust is an important element in *collaborative governance* because it can reduce coordination barriers and increase the effectiveness of collective action. However, trust that rests on previous work relationships also shows that the collaborative process is still highly dependent on certain actors, so it has the potential to be fragile in the event of personnel change. The commitment to the collaborative process in the repatriation service of displaced persons is reflected in the willingness of actors to continue to coordinate despite differences in procedures and time constraints. The results of the study show that differences in working methods do not necessarily stop collaboration, but are discussed through follow-up communication so that the service continues to run. This condition indicates a functional commitment to the collaboration process.

According to Bryson et al. (2020), commitment to collaborative governance is not only measured by the participation of actors, but also by the willingness to maintain cooperation when obstacles arise. In this study, the commitment has not fully developed into an institutionalized strategic commitment, but it still focuses on operational case resolution. Through dialogue and trust built, a common understanding of the purpose of the repatriation service of displaced persons in general has been formed, which is to ensure that displaced people can return to their areas of origin safely and in a safe manner. However, differences in procedures and responses between actors show that the common understanding is still at the operational level and has not been fully standardized. This has an impact on the variety of implementation in the field. However, the collaborative process has resulted in intermediate outcomes in the form of relatively smooth coordination and faster service response to the conditions of displaced people. Quick and Feldman (2021) stated that intermediate outcomes are an important indicator in *collaborative governance* because they reflect the progress of the process before long-term impacts are achieved. In the context of this study, the intermediate results show that collaborative processes have worked, although they have not yet fully resulted in systemic change.

Outcomes in the Implementation of the Repatriation of Displaced Persons

Outcomes in *collaborative governance* are not only understood as the end result in the form of problem solving, but also as a series of achievements that strengthen governance capacity and the sustainability of collaboration. This framework still refers to the model developed by Chris Ansell and Alison Gash, but in its development it has been enriched by various cutting-edge research that emphasizes the dimensions of adaptivity, learning, and public values. The results of the study show that the repatriation of displaced people to their areas of origin is the *main final outcome* of cross-sectoral collaboration. These findings are in line with recent research that states that *collaborative governance* is most effectively applied to complex social problems involving multiple authorities and across administrative areas (Emerson & Nabatchi, 2020). In the context of social services, collaboration allows the integration of resources, authority, and information spread across various actors. The study by Kim and Lim (2022) confirms that the success of collaboration in public service is characterized by the ability of actors to produce concrete solutions that cannot be achieved through sectoral approaches. The repatriation of displaced persons realized in this study shows that collaboration does not stop at formal coordination, but results in real problem solving.

The increase in the effectiveness and speed of services found in this study can be categorized as *intermediate outcomes*. Recent literature emphasizes that intermediate outcomes such as process efficiency, improved coordination, and service acceleration are important indicators of collaborative success before long-term impact is achieved (Ansell, Sørensen, & Torfing, 2020). Research by Bryson et al. (2021) shows that cross-sector collaboration supported by intensive communication and clear division of roles is able to reduce the fragmentation of public services. These findings are relevant to the results of research that show that the repatriation service of displaced persons has become faster because each actor has understood its functions and responsibilities. The outcome in the form of meeting the basic needs of displaced persons during the repatriation process reflects the collaborative orientation on public values and the protection of vulnerable groups. The literature of the last five years confirms that collaborative governance is not only performance-oriented, but also on the creation of *public value* (Nabatchi, Sancino, & Sicilia, 2020). The involvement of NGOs in meeting the basic needs of displaced people supports the findings of Pestoff (2022) who stated that non-governmental actors play a strategic role in *the co-production* of social services, especially in reaching humanitarian needs that are difficult to meet by formal bureaucracy. Thus, this outcome shows that collaboration contributes to a more inclusive and responsive quality of social services.

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The increase in the capacity of the apparatus and the clarity of the handling flow found in this study reflect the existence of *collaborative learning*. Recent research confirms that shared learning is one of the important outcomes of sustainable collaboration (Torfing & Ansell, 2021). A recent study by Cristofoli et al. (2022) shows that cross-sector collaboration in public service encourages the improvement of individual and organizational competencies through the exchange of experience and knowledge. In the context of the repatriation of displaced persons, this learning can be seen from the increased ability of officers to handle cross-regional cases and emergency situations. The outcome in the form of increased mutual awareness of the importance of cross-sector collaboration shows the formation of collaborative social capital. Recent research confirms that collective awareness and shared understanding are key factors for the sustainability of collaborative governance (Sørensen & Torfing, 2021). The realization that the problem of displaced people cannot be partially addressed strengthens the commitment of actors to continue to engage in collaboration. This is in line with the findings of Quick and Feldman (2023) who stated that successful collaborations are supported by actors' willingness to share responsibilities and acknowledge each other's dependence.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. The handling of repatriation services for displaced persons by the Bali Provincial Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Social Service is carried out in stages and coordinated, starting from outreach, data collection, temporary handling, to repatriation to the area of origin. The PPPA Social Service acts as the main coordinator who integrates various actors across sectors to overcome data limitations and case complexity. The implementation of services is not only administratively oriented, but also pays attention to humanitarian aspects, social protection, and sustainability of handling.
2. Based on the results of the study, the implementation of collaborative governance in the repatriation of displaced persons in Bali Province emerged as a response to the complexity of problems that cannot be handled sectorally, characterized by limited data, resources, and cross-regional challenges. The Bali Provincial PPPA Social Service plays the role of the main coordinator who integrates various actors through adaptive institutional design and collaborative processes based on dialogue, trust, and functional commitment. This collaboration not only results in the repatriation of displaced people to their areas of origin as the final outcome, but also produces intermediate outcomes in the form of increasing service effectiveness, meeting basic needs, strengthening the capacity of apparatus, and growing collective awareness of the importance of cross-sectoral cooperation, although the sustainability of the impact still requires institutional strengthening and a more standardized monitoring mechanism.
3. The implementation of collaborative governance in the repatriation service of displaced persons by the Bali Provincial PPPA Social Service still faces various obstacles, especially limited cross-agency coordination, incompleteness of data, limited resources, and differences in commitment and responsiveness between actors. This condition is exacerbated by the lack of a strong standardized institutional arrangement so that collaboration is highly dependent on individual initiatives and existing work relationships. In addition, the focus of collaboration which is still limited to the repatriation stage shows the need to strengthen the post-repatriation follow-up mechanism so that the effectiveness and sustainability of services can be guaranteed.

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